

Research Article

Socio-Ecological Assessment of Bird Species in Akinyele Local Government Area,
Ibadan, Oyo State

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Abstract

The study was based mainly on the socio-ecological assessment of bird species in Akinyele Local Government with reference to five villages. The study examined the location and the assessment of the bird species and the problem encountered in the area of damage done by the birds on agricultural produce. The villages chosen include Moniya, Onidundun, Akinyele, Ijaye and Isdigba. A total of 100 questionnaires were administered of which 20 questionnaires were distributed to each village, 88 were retrieved and analyzed using Descriptive statistical tools such as frequency count and simple percentages. Lists of some bird species within the study area include Vulture, Owl, Cattle Eaglet, Hawk, Pigeon, and Parrot among others. The study revealed that some birds are regarded as sacred, while some like vultures are forbidden to be consumed by anyone. Some birds are regarded as pests because of damages they cause to farm produce; these include maize, paper, cassava, cocoyam and yam. It is known that the stage of damage is the germination and growing stages. The economic benefits of some birds are; some bird's serves as time indicator, some are used for medicinal purpose, some serve as source of protein and some serves as sources of income. Also, some are predators to agricultural pest like grasshoppers. Recommendations were made that the government should make law against the illegal hunting of birds and enlighten farmers on how to protect their farms against bird attack. Research should be done to investigate the medicinal values of birds.

Keywords: Bird species, socio-ecological, Akinyele Local Government Area, assessment, villages

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Introduction

It is a general belief that birds are created by God to live all over the earth. They are capable of doing wonderful things like taking - off, flying with twists and turns, soaring and diving, and landing again on a small branch. There are about 8,600 species of birds in the world today and they are found everywhere (Chan, 2001).

Birds are unique in the animal kingdom for two reasons, first, all birds have feathers and secondly, all birds live in a hurry. Everything about a bird is fast. They breathe faster than any other animals. Their hearts beat faster and their temperature is higher. Birds have a backbone and are warm blooded i.e. their body temperature remains the same even in differing temperature. They lay eggs and defend themselves with a bill or a beak. All birds have wings but not all birds fly (Abe, 1998).

According to Zhou (2004), birds are bipedal, warm blooded animals that lay eggs. They range in sizes from 5cm e.g. Bee humming bird to 5cm e.g. ostrich (2.7m). According to Clarke (2004), all birds have forelimbs modified as wings and most can fly, with some exceptions, including ratites, penguins and numbers of diverse endemic island species.

Birds also have unique digestive and respiratory systems. Birds play a vital role in the balance of nature as some eat insects, pests, fruits, and seeds of plants. Birds are often best for scattering and propagating seeds on the surface of land. Other values of birds are eggs and meat for consumption; feathers are for pillows, quilts and clothing as reported by (Akegbejo, 1996). Man has also written poetry, stories and songs about birds. Birds have also become symbols for human values, for instance owls mean wisdom, and the dove represents peace while the eagle signifies political power.

Some birds are carnivorous (bird of prey) such as Hawk, Eagle, Venture, Lizard, Buzzard, and Owl all are living on flesh and prey on smaller reptiles, rodent, birds, fish, etc. There are other birds such as dove, parrot, peathen, peacock, ostrich, etc that feed on grains like millet, maize, rice, beans, and nuts. Birds (birds of prey) live in the open country and dense forest of Africa and America.

Ornithology is the scientific study of birds and started in the 1700's. This study is then geared towards evolving strategies that will ensure harmonious integration of the need of the people and a sustainable utilization of the wildlife. There is a common belief that all natural resources either plant or animal are gifts from God and thus inexhaustible. From time, immemorial, man as an individual or as a group is depended upon one another and other natural resources and the existing conditions in this environment for survival. Therefore, this study is to determine the

Socio-ecological assessment of bird species in Akinyele Local Government Area, Ibadan, Oyo State.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State. The Secretariat of Akinyele Local Government Area was situated at Moniya in Ibadan. The villages that are situated within the Akinyele Local Government Area include the following: (i) Moniya (ii) Alabata (iii) Araba (iv) Oni-dundu (v) Langbeja (vi) Ijaye (vii) Mele (viii) Akinyele (ix) Motoso (x) Idigba etc.

Sampling Techniques

A total of one hundred (100) questionnaires were administered to the people residing in Akinyele Local Government Area. Five villages were chosen at random (using stratified random sampling) as a source of information with twenty (20) questionnaires in order to allow for proper determination of the socio-ecological assessment of bird species in the area. The villages chosen are;

- (1) Moniya (2) Oni-Dundu (3) Akinyele (4) Ijaye (5) Idigba

Methodology

The research was conducted by using three methods of data collection

- (a) Questionnaire (b) Oral interview (c) Direct observation

A Questionnaire

Well-structured questionnaires were administered among the residents in the selected villages around the Akinyele Local Government Area. Assistance was given to respondents who had difficulty in reading and writing. Both men and women who belonged to different profession filled the questionnaire and, this provided necessary information for the work.

B Oral interview

In each of the selected villages, consultations with the members in the communities (including individuals, hunters, farmers and youths) were done in the form of an interview. Both adult men and women were interviewed in each sampled village. The use of local language during the oral interview was understandably conceived as the respondents have implicit confidence and discussed freely. This contributed immensely to the success of data collection.

C Direct Observation

On site assessment of Akinyele Local Government Area was carried out through all entrances that lead to Akinyele Local Government Area. Many farms and settlements were also observed.

Thorough assessment of the Akinyele Local Government Area was made possible through this method.

Data Analysis

All data collected were subjected to appropriate statistical tools which include descriptive statistic such as frequency count, and simple percentage.

Results and Discussions

Table 1 revealed the number of villages, questionnaire distributed and the number of Respondents. Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents based on their gender, Age range, Education level and Religion respectively. The male gender has 68%, while the female has 32%. In age range, the first age group has 16%; followed by 17%; 27% and 40% respectively. It also shows that those in their range of 51-60 are mostly respondents than others.

In the education level, it also shows that various respondents are different e.g. 43% of the respondents are those with non-formal educational qualification. While 41% and 16% has primary and secondary education background respectively. The implication of this is that most of the respondents are those with no or low educational level due to the fact that the acquisition of practical knowledge of the farming and hunting of their family.

In religion, it also shows that 32% and 23% of the respondents are Muslims and Christianity respectively, while 45% are traditional which shows that the respondents is practiced mostly by the traditional people.

Table 1: Questionnaire distributed and the number of Respondents.

Name of village	Number of distributed	Number of respondents
Akinyele	20	17
Idi-Igba	20	16
Ijayc	20	20
Moniya	20	20
Oni-Dundu	20	15
Total	100	88

Table 2: Respondents of Gender, Age range, Education Level and Religion

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	60	68
Female	28	32
Age Range		
20 below	–	.
21-30	14	16
31-40	15	17
41-50	24	27
51-60	35	40
Education Qualification	38	43
No formal		
Primary Education	36	41
Secondary Education	14	16
Religion		
Islam	26	32
Christianity	20	23
Traditional	40	45

Table 3: List of Bird Specie within the Study Area

Local Name	Common Name	Zoological Name
Igungun	Vulture	<i>Gyps africanus</i>
Owiwi	Owl	<i>Tyto alba</i>
Lekeleke	Cattle egret	<i>Ardeola ibis</i>
Asa	Hawk	<i>Polemaetus bellicose</i>
Elulu	Senegal conceal	<i>Cetropes senegalensis</i>
Kowee	Levaillant coucou	<i>Clamator levaillant</i>
Eyele	Pigeon	<i>Alcidae.</i>
Adaba	Red turtle eye	<i>Streptopelia</i> <i>senitorquata</i>
Ayekooto	Parrot	<i>. Ara araranuna</i>
Kanakana	Lizard Buzzard	<i>Kaupifalcon</i> <i>monogrammicus</i>
Opere/Tinfm	Bronze Mannikin	<i>Condura bicobr</i>
Pepeye	Duck	<i>Cygnus atratus</i>
Awo/Etu	Guinea fowl	<i>Nomads meleageris</i>
Aparo	Double sparred francolin	<i>Francolimis bicalcaratus</i>

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Table 4: List of Sacred birds and People's Belief

Common Name	Reason	Beliefs
Vulture	Forbidden to be killed and consumed by anyone.	Smallpox (Igbona) will attack whoever eats it.
Cattle -Egret	It must not be killed and eaten by anyone	It's white body turns black when killed and that this mean a curse on whoever eats it.
Akala - Magbo	It must not be killed and eaten by anyone	If it is accidentally killed it must not be made known to people and scarifies must be made to avert curses that can befall the killer
Levaillant	If it is seen on the roof of any house making sound, through the consequences depend on the type of sound that bird made	It reveal death when sighted on house top roof making some stirringly sound or it make a bad sign
Senegal coucel	It is responsible for rainfall/ precipitation	There is a curse on whoever kills it because it will affect rainfall in the area

The list of bird species within the study area was presented in Table 3. Altering the law backing the beliefs can lead to diseases and death was presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Name of Crops Damaged by Birds and Stage of Destruction

Crop	Bird causing the damage	Stage which crops are damaged
Maize	Bush fowl	Germination or growing state
Pepper	Weaver bird	Flowering
Yam	Flankolin	Growing stage
Cassava	Sparrow	Germination
Plantain	Plantain eater	Germination

Table 5 shows the level of damages cause by the birds either in flowering or germination stage to these particular crops mentioned above.

Table 6: Seasonal Variations in Availability Birds

Birds	Wet season	Dry season
Wet season	Early wet season	-
Dry season	Throughout wet	-
Vulture	Wet season	Dry season
Owl	Wet season	-

Table 6 shows that only vulture and owl are the bird species that are affected by the wet seasonal variation because bird species are affected by rainfall as it will not allow them to take off flight easily. Due to belief of the people, there are some bird species that are regarded as sacred. Strong beliefs have been attached to it and people still respect it i.e. the bird species. Some of this bird species and the reason why they are regarded as sacred as well as their beliefs are listed in Table 4.

Table 7: Benefits Derivable from Birds

Bird Specie	Medicinal Use	Parts of Birds
Vulture	Epilepsy	Intestine
Owl	Rheumatism	Blood
Eagle	Chronic headache	Head
Pigeon	Eye worms	Feathers
Dove	High blood pressure	Heart
Hawk	Diabetes	Gizzard
Vulture	Chicken/small pox	Blood + intestine
Owl	Blood cure	Intestines + blood
Sparrow	Isiju	Blood

Conclusion

From the result obtained, it could be seen that the socio-economics importance of the bird cannot be overemphasized. It has a positive impact and a negative impact on both human and agricultural crops. It is hoped that with more awareness in the area of bird survey, tourism will be improved upon.

Recommendation

With the study, enlightenment should be made to people about the importance of birds in the society. Also the economy aspect of bird has really been an eye opener to the hays tourisms should be worked upon and the conservation and protection of the birds. Government should ensure the protection of their birds by promulgation of the law that guides against illegal hunting of their birds. Also the medicinal aspect of the birds must also be put into serious considerations.

References

Abe Akinola, (1998). *A Handbook on Zoo and Parks in Nigeria. Zoo Education*, University Of Ibadan Zoo. Pp.14.

Akegbejo Samsons Y., (1996). *Introduction to Wildlife Management in Nigeria*. (Thesis), Akure, Nigeria. Pp.12.

Chan K., (2001). *Partial Migration in Australian Land Birds; A Review Of Useful Birds of Australia*. Pp. 281-292

Clarke, Julia A. (2004). "*Morphology, Phylogenetic Taxonomy, and Systematic Of Ichthyornis and Apatornis (Avialae "Ornithurae")*". Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History Pp.286.

Zhou, Zhougbe (2004). "*The Origin and Early Evolution of Birds: Discoveries, Disputes and Perspectives from fossil Evidence*" Baltimore: John Hopkins University press. Pp 91.